

IMPERIAL

Prospects for an Upgraded Near Detector for Hyper - Kamiokande ND280++

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Hyper Kamiokande

Beamline

- Upgraded
→ 1.3MW
(2.5 x higher power)

Near Detectors

- ND280 as magnetised near detector (plans to be taken over by Hyper-K)
- IWCD: Intermediate Water Cherenkov Detector – movable to sample different off axis angles
- Will constrain neutrino interaction uncertainties

Far Detector

- Water Cherenkov far detector: 188.4 kton fiducial volume (8.4 x Super-K)
- Will measure $P(\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e)$ vs $P(\bar{\nu}_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\nu}_e)$ to infer CP violating phase

See Talk by **Róbert Králik** for status of Hyper-K

Super Fine Grain Detector

“High angle” time projection chambers (HATPCs)

Fine Grain Detectors made of alternating “X” and “Y” layers of plastic scintillator bars read out by WLS fibres

Gaseous argon time projection chambers (TPCs)

ND280++

Super Fine Grain Detector

“High angle” time projection chambers (HATPCs)

?????????

Physics Goals

- Time to reach goal of 5σ exclusion of $\delta_{CP} = 0$ can be drastically reduced by improved systematics
- As such, near detectors (which we use to constrain systematics) become very important for HK
- For ND280++ Want to target main systematics for HK and maximise complementarity with IWCD

Physics goal	Measurement
$\sigma(\nu_e/\bar{\nu}_e)$ in H_2O	High-stat $\nu_e/\bar{\nu}_e$ H_2O
ν_μ vs $\bar{\nu}_\mu$	Muon charge
ν_e vs $\bar{\nu}_e$	Electron charge
IWCD escaping energy	> 1 GeV μ and e^-
Low-p hadrons	Sub-mm resolution
Neutrons kinematics	Large mass, sub-ns

→ largest source of uncertainty on δ_{CP}

Complementary to IWCD and will enhance the ability of ND280 to characterise ν_μ and $\bar{\nu}_\mu$ interactions

ND280++ Design

ND280++ Reference Design

Input to EU Strategy update
(arXiv:2506.16641)

- We have a working reference design with a number of different possible sub-detector designs under consideration
- Large mass of scintillator
- Large mass of inactive water
- 1 vertical TPC
- Refurbish the Electromagnetic CALorimeter

See Talk by
Daniel Ferlewicz
for R&D status

Inactive Water Detector

Hyper-Fine Grain Detector
Possible use of water based scintillator →

Alternate ND280++ Design LiquidO Based Hyper FGD

- LiquidO uses opaque scintillator to confine light near production point instead of using optically separated scintillating units to construct a detector
- Then read out light using optical fibers

- Can use structure of light distribution to possibly get better resolution than equivalent segmented detector
- Such detectors have been experimentally proven to work ([arXiv:2507.13864](https://arxiv.org/abs/2507.13864), [arXiv:2503.02541](https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.02541))
- Can be impractical to simulate all photons produced
- need to parameterise simulation to get speed needed for high stats studies

Alternate ND280++ Design – LiquidO Based Hyper FGD

- Implemented parameterised simulation which is ~50,000X faster than using the Geant4 optical simulation
- Now able to practically run large scale detector simulations within ND280 software framework fast enough to get some proper statistics

Alternate ND280++ Design – LiquidO Based Hyper FGD

- Have also been working on reconstruction algorithm to turn these projections into 3D events and fit tracks

- Simulation details
- 300 MeV muon
 - 200 MeV Proton
 - 1mm scatter
 - 5m absorption
 - 10mm fiber pitch
 - Simulate fiber attenuation, photon trapping but *NO SENSORS OR ELECTRONICS*

Apply simple peak finding algorithm in each projection

Require 3 neighbouring 2D "peak hits" to build 3D hits – then fit tracks however you like

Quite simple procedure also works nicely for Neut events

Alternate Scintillator Designs

- Single scintillating cubes, same as SuperFGD but improved injection moulding
- Single layers of glued plastic scintillator cubes
- Synergy with FASER:
 - R&D on 48x48 cubes layers
- 3D Printed scintillator R&D ongoing by 3Det collaboration

JINST 16 P12010 (2021)

Alternate Scintillator Designs

- Sing
- Super
- mou
- Sing
- scint
- Synchron
- R&
- 3D F
- ongo

Possible Extension To Hyper-FGD

- Additional hydrocarbon detector with different amount of hydrogen – perform subtraction based measurement of neutrino + H interactions
 - Simplest case is polystyrene (CH) (HyperFGD) and mineral oil (CH₂)
- Can be used to benchmark, and then combined with TKI based measurements

Summary

- Hyper-K CP violation sensitivity will be dominated by systematic uncertainties
- ND280++ is a possible upgrade to the ND280 near detector which would happen after 2030 – a few years after the start of HK data taking
- Ongoing simulation studies to optimise the design, currently working towards physics studies
- Numerous R&D projects ongoing for novel detector technologies
- ND280++ presents a unique opportunity for new institutions to join Hyper-K with exciting developments in physics and R&D

Backup

Section Subtitle

Summary

True normal ordering (known)
 $\sin^2\theta_{13}=0.0218 \pm 0.0007$, $\sin^2\theta_{23}=0.528$, $\Delta m_{32}^2=2.509 \times 10^{-3} \text{eV}^2/c^4$

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ND280 Upgrade

June 2024 Run

ND280++ Design – “Scintillating Fiber (SciFi)”

Motivation: Fine-grain 3D particle tracking

- ~ 0.2 mm plastic scintillator fibers in alternating X and Y layers
- Extremely high granularity tracking
- Main challenge: reading out such a large number of channels

ND280++ Design – “Inactive Water Detector”

- ~0.2 mm plastic scintillator fibers in alternating X and Y layers with ~1cm “inactive” water layers between
- Extremely high granularity tracking, large water mass
- Main challenges: reading out such a large number of channels

- Ongoing R&D at Tohoku U

ND280++ Design – “Hyper FGD”

- Same concept as the super FGD (in ND280 upgrade) but larger mass
- 1 cm plastic scintillator cubes read out by WLS fibres
- Main challenges: aligning fibers/cubes during installation

ND280++ Design – WBLS based Hyper FGD

See: N. Onda et al,
arXiv:2507.18893

- Similar concept but with fixed segmented cell structure filled with water based liquid scintillator (WBLS)
- Same target as HK
- Similar spatial resolution as SFGD
- Being developed and prototyped at ETH

- Want a way of directly mapping energy deposited in the detector to light collected in fibers:
- For 1,000 points in 10x10x10 grid:
 - Simulate “photon bomb” (100,000 isotropic photons = ~10x yield per MeV)
 - Keep track of fraction of photons from that point end up in each fiber
 - Use this to build a detector response “map”
 - Use map as lookup when running simulation
- Time per event (mu + proton pgun) gone from ~1.5 hours → O(0.1) seconds

● = photon bomb start points

- Perform very simple “peak finding” algorithm

- For peaks, take weighted average of 3 nearest neighbours, checking that they monotonically decrease
- Do separately in each projection

- Use “peak hits” to build 3D hits

- Require 3 neighbouring 2D “peak hits” to build a 3D hit

- Fit tracks by whatever method you like

- Works surprisingly well, even on more complex Neut events

